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The Influence of Gender, Age, Training and Experience on Teachers' Motivation in Ado and Efon Local Government Areas, Ekiti State, Nigeria

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Research Article

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the influence of gender, age, training and experience of secondary school teachers on their motivation. The descriptive research design of the survey type was used for study. The population consisted of all the teachers in Ado and Efon Local Government Areas in Ekiti State. The sample comprises 500 teachers from 18 secondary schools in the two local government areas. Stratified proportional random sampling was used to select the sample for the study. A self-designed questionnaire tagged "Questionnaire on Teachers' Gender, Age, Training and Experience and Conditions of Service" (QTGATECS) was used to collect the data for the study. The instrument was validated by research experts in Educational Management and Tests and Measurement Departments of Ekiti State University. The data were analysed using frequency counts, percentage scores, t-test. The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The result shows that there was no significant difference in the motivation of male and female, untrained and trained, experienced and inexperienced teachers. However, there was a significant difference between young and old teachers in their motivation. It was concluded that teachers in Ado and Efon Local Government Areas had poor motivation and was recommended that teachers' motivation on the job should be improved by principals and government who should ensure that teachers' welfare, training, salary, loans and teaching aid requirements and other needs are adequately met.

Keywords: Gender, Age, Training, Experience, Teachers, Motivation.

INTRODUCTION

There is no greater factor for the social economic and political advancement than a good educational system (Fafunwa, 1980). For successful schools and educational systems, teachers are very vital. In view of this, Adedeji (1998), Oguntoye (2002) and Omotayo (2007) agreed that teachers are very important to the success of the school system in achieving its goals and objectives. Fasanmi (1996) opined that the standard of education in any country cannot be above the standard of its teachers. Lornah, Sirima and poipoi (2010) opined that job satisfaction is essential to the continuing growth of educational systems around the world and teachers are crucial element of educational opportunity structures. Teachers must be ready to discharge their duties and obligations in order to achieve successful, effective and efficient teaching and learning processes in the educational system.

However, these teachers appear to have complained that they were not well motivated on the job and adequate incentives were not given to them on the job. Teachers seem to complain that they did not enjoy adequate in- service training, workshops and seminars. Rewards, incentives and other remunerations appeared not to be enjoyed by them as they should. Teachers also appear to complain of poor welfare packages like loans. Goke (2012) noted that teachers complained that their needs were not fulfilled according to their expectations. In the same vein, Nbina (2012) opined that teachers of today are buffered by many challenges which dampen their moral and lower motivation to perform effectively.

Koontz, O'Donnel & Wehrich (1980), Owuamanam (1991) and Ibukun (1997) agreed that what is a source of inducement or motivation to one person may fail to influence the behaviour of others. Individuals differ in the value they attach to inducement. This means that what motivates a worker to work hard may not even motivate another worker at all. Koontz et al (1980) explained motivators as those things which induce an individual to perform. In the same vein, Ibukun (1979) asserted that it is obvious that man has several sources of motivation. What satisfied one individual and motivates him may not act as a source of drive for another individual. He added that sources of motivation increase in value and complexity depending on the age and social status of the individual. Koontz et al (1980) discussed the report of a study carried out in America by Health

and Education Department in 1973 which concluded that the primary cause of satisfaction of workers is the nature of their work or the quality of their working life.

Fatile (1998) opined that teachers must be provided with incentives, resources and facilities that will enable them perform effectively and maximally. Cogan (1975) noted that teachers themselves may internalise a low opinion of their teaching role and this undoubtedly would hamper the effectiveness of their work. Ibukun (1997) noted that the behaviours typical of an unmotivated individual are frustration, aloofness, withdrawal, clique formation, defensiveness, avoidance of issues, laziness on duty, temperamental emotion regression, fear and projection ascribing failure to others. Fagbamiye (1981) asserted that the poor public image of teachers would wreak untold havoc on self image and confidence of teachers who remains in their classrooms and would be a major contributor to why teachers drop out of the profession. According to him, this is the root cause of the falling standard of education in Nigeria. Abiri (1970) observed that teaching in Nigeria is rarely enthusiastically chosen as a career, owing partly to the erstwhile relatively poor remuneration and low status of teachers.

Bennett, Gottesman, Rock & Cerullo (1993) opined that gender and behaviour of teachers affect their judgments of academic skills. Martin and Harsh (2005) opined that academic motivation and engagement are the same for male and female teachers. They averred further that, academic motivation and engagement does not significantly vary as a function of teachers' gender and in terms of academic motivation. That is, male teachers do not fare any better than female teachers. On the contrary, The International Rescue Committee (2009) opined that gender is a factor in determining teachers' roles, responsibilities as status in families and communities. Gender impacts teachers' perception priorities for the future. This contrast between Martins et al, (2005) and the International Rescue Committee (2009) could be as a result of human and research methodology factors. Bishay (1996) discovered that job satisfaction and motivation correlated significantly with responsibility levels, gender, age, years of teaching experience and activities. Karabenick & Conley (2011) noted that on the average, teachers reported that they were positively motivated to participate in Professional Development.

Burkar, Idris & Bukar (2011) asserted that teachers are not being sponsored to pursue higher academic training through study leave and in-service training and there is the problem of poor attendance of teachers at academic seminars/workshops and conferences. Harris (2012) noted that a good administrator will help their teachers by finding positive ways to encourage them to attend courses, workshop and activities that will ultimately help them to become better teachers. Nbina (2012) opined that teachers of today are buffered by many challenges which dampen their moral and lower their motivation to perform effectively and this could have an adverse effect on the educational system.

Fringe benefits have been reluctantly granted to teachers when compared with their counterparts in the private sectors. This results in teachers' dissatisfaction with their job. However, in view of the need to know the level of teachers' motivation and the disparities in the studies on teachers' motivation in relation to their gender, age, training and experience, this study will examine the influence of teachers' gender, age, training and experience on their level of motivation.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to investigate the Influence of gender, age, training and experience on teachers' motivation in Ado and Efon Local Government Areas in Ekiti State. The study will find out the extent to which teachers are motivated on the job.

Research Questions

1. To what extent are teachers motivated on their job?
2. Does gender, age, training and experience influence teachers' motivation?

Research Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference between male and female teachers' motivation.
2. There is no significant difference between young and old teachers' motivation.
3. There is no significant difference between trained and untrained teachers' motivation.
4. There is no significant difference between experienced and less experienced teachers' motivation.

METHODOLOGY

The study is a descriptive research of the survey type. The population consisted of all teachers in public secondary schools in Ado and Efon Local Government Areas. The sample for the study consisted of 500 teachers selected from 15 out of 18 schools in the two local governments. There are 1,415 teachers in Ado and Avon Local Government Areas i.e. 1,253 in Ado and 162 in Efon Local Government Areas. Sixty five (65) teachers were selected from Efon Local Government Area, while four hundred and thirty five (435) teachers were

selected from Ado Local Government Area. Stratified proportional random sampling was used to select the sample used for the study.

One self-designed questionnaire, tagged "Questionnaire on Teachers' Gender, Age, Training, Experience and their Motivation" (QTGATEM) was used to collect the necessary data for the study. Research experts in the Department of Tests and Measurement and Educational Management of Ekiti State University validated the instrument. The test-retest method was used to test the reliability of the instrument and the reliability coefficient stood at 0.72. Frequency counts, percentage scores and t-test analysis were used to analyse the data collected. The hypotheses formulated were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Research question: To what extent are the teachers motivated on their job?

Table 1: Teachers' motivation on the job

S/N	Item	Responses of Teachers		% of Agree	% of Disagree
		Agree	Disagree		
1.	I am well motivated on the job	139	361	27	73
2.	On the job training is organised for teachers regularly	83	417	17	83
3.	Salaries and allowances are paid to teachers regularly	139	361	28	72
4.	I do not lack teaching equipment	61	439	12	88
5.	Workshops were organised by government for teachers for development	82	418	16	84
6.	There is free health care for teachers	30	470	6	94
7.	Housing and car loans are given to teachers who applied for them	146	354	29	71
8.	Verbal/ written commendations were given to teachers who excelled in their schools	135	365	27	73
Average		102	398	20	80

The result in table 1 shows that teachers were not well motivated on the job as 73% of the respondents claimed that they were not while the remaining (27%) out of the total of 500 respondents claimed the they were motivated. In the same vein, 83% claimed that on the job trainings were not organised for teachers while 449(88%) claimed that they lack teaching equipment. As evident on table 1, 354 (71%) claimed that housing and car loans were not given to teachers who applied for them. 470 (94%) of the respondents indicated that there were no free health care for teachers. Of the teachers, 365 (73%) also claimed that verbal and written commendations were not given to teachers who excelled in their schools. On the average 20% of the teacher respondents claimed that they were motivated on the job while 80% indicated that they were not motivated on the job. This means that teachers' motivation in secondary schools in Ado and Efon Local Government was poor and inadequate.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between male and female teachers' motivation

Table 2: t-test for male and female teachers' motivation

Group	N	\bar{X}	SD	df	t-cal	table-value
Male teachers	245	29.44	6.10	498	1.14	1.96
Female teachers	255	28.81	6.16			

P >0.05 (Not Significant)

Table 2 shows that t-cal of 1.14 is less than table value of 1.96. This implies that the hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference between male and female teachers' motivation is not rejected. That is, there is no significant difference between male and female teachers' motivation.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between young and old teachers' motivation

Table 3: t-test for young and old teachers' motivation

<i>Group</i>	<i>N</i>	\bar{X}	<i>SD</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>t-cal</i>	<i>table-value</i>
Young teachers	261	28.48	6.57	498	2.43*	1.96
Old teachers	239	29.81	5.55			

*P >0.05 (Not Significant)

Table 3 revealed that t-cal of 2.43 is greater than the table value of 1.96 at the degree of freedom of 498. By implication, the hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference between young and old teachers' motivation is rejected. It means that there is significant difference between old and young teachers' motivation that is there is disparity in their level of motivation.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference between trained and untrained teachers' motivation

Table 4: t-test for untrained and trained teachers' motivation

<i>Group</i>	<i>N</i>	\bar{X}	<i>SD</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>t-cal</i>	<i>table-value</i>
Untrained teachers	147	30.34	6.36	498	2.90*	1.96
Trained teachers	353	28.61	5.97			

*P <0.05 (Significant)

Table 4 shows that t-cal which is 2.90 is greater than table value of 1.96 at the degree of freedom of 498 and at 0.05 level of significance. This implies that hypothesis 3 which states that there is no significant difference between trained and untrained teachers' motivation is rejected. This means that there is a significant difference between trained and untrained teacher's motivation on the job.

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant difference between experienced and inexperienced teachers' motivation

Table 5: t-test for experienced and inexperienced teachers' motivation

<i>Group</i>	<i>N</i>	\bar{X}	<i>SD</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>t-cal</i>	<i>table-value</i>
Experienced teachers	163	29.08	6.54	497	0.14	1.96
Inexperienced teachers	336	29.16	5.92			

P >0.05 (Not Significant)

Table 5 shows that t-cal which is 0.14 is less than table value of 1.96 at the degree of freedom of 497 and at 0.5 level of significance. This means that hypothesis 4 which states that there is no significant difference between experienced and inexperienced teachers' motivation is not rejected. It means there is no significant difference between experienced and inexperienced teachers motivation.

DISCUSSION

The study revealed that teachers' motivation on the job was poor. This explains teachers' poor discharge of their duties and their dissatisfaction with the job. This may not be unconnected with government's nonchalant attitude towards the provision of adequate remunerations, incentives/rewards, training and welfare of teachers and School principals' neglect of their responsibilities towards their teachers' wellbeing. This is in line with Burkar, Idris & Bukar (2011). Teachers were not rewarded for hard work. This agrees with Nbina (2012) and Gokce (2012) but it contrasts with Karabenick & Conley (2011).

The result of this study also revealed that there is no significant difference between male and female teachers motivation. This could be as a result of teachers of both sexes being treated alike and the same rules guide them on the job. This agrees with Martin and Harsh (2005) but in contrast with Bennett, Gottesman, Rock & Cerullo (1993) and The International Rescue Committee (2009). The study found that there is a significant difference between young and old teachers' motivation. Old teachers were motivated more than Young teachers. This is likely to give the older teacher more sense of belonging and probably some remunerations/privileges. The

young teachers are between 18 -39 years while old teachers are between 40 -60 years of age. This is not unconnected with the fact that older teachers are given higher responsibilities and duty posts, such as registrars, house masters/mistress, form masters/coordinators, while younger teachers are not. This agrees with Ibukun (1997) but contrasts with Bichay (1996).

The study showed that there was a significant difference between trained and untrained teachers. This means that trained teachers were more motivated than the untrained teachers. The implication of this is that the trained teachers would be happier than the untrained teachers which could affect their performance on the job. The reason for these disparities is not unconnected with the fact that untrained teachers felt that they do not belong to the profession, so they did not appreciate whatever motivation they were given while the professionals are satisfied with the little or poor motivation that they were given. The untrained teachers expected more from the profession. This disagrees with Bishay (1996). The study also revealed that there was no significant difference in experienced and inexperienced teachers in their motivation. The reason that could be advanced for this agreement of their assessment could be that both categories of teachers saw their profession in the same light. This also agrees with Bishay (1996).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, it could be concluded that teachers were not well motivated on the job in secondary schools in Ado and Efon Local Government Areas. Sex was not a factor in teachers' motivation. However, age was a factor in motivation. Professionalism is a factor in motivation as trained teachers were motivated more than untrained teachers. Conversely, experience is not a factor in teachers' motivation in secondary schools in Ado and Efon Local Government Areas.

Based on the findings of this study, the Government should adequately motivate their teachers by making sure that their welfare, remuneration, training and other needs are taken care of and the profession should be made attractive so that all categories of teachers will appreciate the teaching profession and be more committed to their job. Also, school principals should do all in their power to make their teachers happy on the job by giving them a sense of belonging in their schools. Due to the fact that sex and experience are not factors in teachers' motivation, all teachers should be well motivated on the job so that they will continue to do their job well. In view of the fact that age and training are factors in teachers' motivation, teaching should be made more attractive and enjoyable so that teachers, irrespective of their age would be happy on the job. Government should also ensure that teachers enjoy adequate in-service training and workshops so that both trained and untrained teachers would benefit and feel motivated as teachers.

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